

Student's Performance Prediction using Hybrid Machine Learning Classifiers

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Abstract—Many educational organizations such as schools, universities and training centers try to predict their students' performance in advance, in order to enhance the overall performance of these educational system. In general, educational systems has a huge data (i.e., big data) that can be extracted from several resources such as exam papers, statistics about virtual courses, and e-learning management systems. In this paper, we employed several machine learning classifiers (i.e., One Dimensional Convolutional Neural Network (1D-CNN), nearest neighbors (kNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Naïve Bayes (NB), and Artificial Neural Network (ANN)) to predict the students' performance. Moreover, we applied binary genetic algorithm (BGA) as wrapper feature selection algorithm to reduce the data dimensionality and enhance the overall performance of used classifiers. A real dataset obtained from UCI machine learning repository is used to evaluate the proposed hybrid approach. The reported results show the performance of 1D-CNN outperforms other methods with an accuracy equal to 91%.

I. INTRODUCTION

Educational systems usually has a big data that can be employed to discover enhance the overall performance of educational systems [1]. This big data can be generated from several resources such as: student exam papers (i.e., marks), e-learning log file, admissions/registration data, and virtual courses. This big data can be examined and manipulated to find a meaningful knowledge. In general, predicting students' performance is challenging that many educational systems (e.g., schools, universities and training centers) try to handle it every year [2], [3]. Predicting students' performance at earlier stage will enhance the educational leaders and tutors to find a set of solutions to prevent negative performance of students [4]. Tutors and course coordinators can find strong strategy's to enhance the performance of their students. Moreover, students' performance prediction process can enhance the enrolment policies for educational organization and helps students to overcome their negative performance.

Educational Data Mining approach (EDM) can be used to improve students' learning process [5]. Finding a meaningful knowledge can help the tutors and decision-makers to find an optimal or near optimal solution for their students. However, the ability of tutors and decision-makers to analyze and manipulate the educational data is limited. As a result, this

educational data needs a computerized approach to manipulate them. Moreover, The two main components that are used collect, analyze, and report all educational data are EDM and learning analytics (LA) [6]. In simple, EDM focuses either on enhancing the learning process (i.e., applied research) or extracting knowledge in order to enhance the understanding of the learning process (i.e., pure research) [7].

One of the most well-known methods of handling complex educational data is Machine learning (ML) methods. Every year, educational systems such as Learning Management Systems (LMS) have a large amount of data year after year. This huge data should be processed correctly using ML methods to extract the hidden knowledge and classify students to excellent, good, and weak students [8].

In this work, we applied a wrapper feature selection algorithm to find the most valuable features related to the student's performance. The dataset used in this paper consists of 32 features (i.e., inputs). Understanding the features that reduce the performance of the students is valuable information either for tutors and decision-makers to find robust strategies to avoid negative performance.

This paper has two research questions which are:

- Determine the most valuable features that affects on students performance.
- Highlight the performance of several machine learning classifiers for predicting students' performance.

The rest of this paper organized as follows: Section II presents the related works of machine learning and feature selection in the area of students performance prediction . Section?? explores the proposed method. Section IV presents the students' performance dataset. Section VI explores the obtained results and a deep discussion about it. Finally, Section VII presents the finding and future work of this paper.

II. RELATED WORKS

The concept of EDM attracts many researcher in the optimization and machine learning world due to the complexity of educational data [9]. Several research papers investigated the EDM deeply [10], [11]. In general, all published works, the educational data is collected either from e-learning systems

or surveys. Here, we will focus on students' performance prediction only.

Several approaches have been used to tackle EDM using different machine learning methods (i.e., clustering, sequential pattern analysis, web mining, and classification). The main goal of employing these methods is to find an accurate and robust model to predict students' performance. Yang and Li [12] predicted the students' performance in high schools using artificial neural network (ANN). The dataset is collected from 60 different high schools. The authors proposed a student attribute model (SAM) to presents the collected features (attributes). The reported results show the ability of predicting students' performance in an early stage. Rana and Garg [13] applied two machine learning methods (i.e., NB and ANN). The authors used WEAK software to predict the students' performance. The obtained results show that NB is more robust and accurate compared to ANN. Kesumawati and Utari [14] employed support vector machine (SVM) and NB to predict the time for graduation. The reported results show that SVM is better than NB.

Harwati et al. [15] studied the students' performance based on many demographic features (i.e., gender, GPA, grades in specific courses, and attendance ratio). The authors applied k-means clustering algorithm to cluster students into three groups (i.e., smart, normal and weak students). Bharara et al. [16] employed k-means clustering algorithm to find the most important features to discover the hidden relationships between the collected features and students' performance. Trivedi et al. [17] explores the benefits of computerized assessment to enhance the overall performance for students in their exams. de Morais et al. [18] studied the performance of their students for an English e-learning course. The authors applied employed k-means clustering algorithm to group their students into five groups (i.e., Expert, Good, Regular, Bad and Criticism). Then, they applied a regression method to predict the students' performance. The reported results show the importance of the proposed approach of understanding students' performance.

Saarela et al. [19] developed an intelligent system for math question that can predict the difficulty level of each question and if the students can solve them or not. Prasada Rao et al. [20] programmed three different machine learning methods (i.e. J48, Naïve-Bayes and Random forest) to predict the student's performance. The dataset consists of 200 students from two departments (i.e., computer science and engineering). The reported results show an excellent performance of Random forest compared to other methods.

Turabieh et al. [21] applied an enhanced version of Harris Hawks optimization (HHO) algorithm as a feature selection algorithm to determine the most valuable features that is related to the students' performance. The authors proposed a novel update method to control the diversity of HHO. The reported results show that the proposed enhancement can explore the EDM better than the original HHO. The authors applied four machine learning algorithms (i.e., k-nearest neighbors (kNN), Layered recurrent neural network (LRNN), NB, and ANN) to evaluate the selected features. the reported results show that

LRNN is an excellent classifier with accuracy 92%.

It is clear that, several machine learning methods can be used to predict students' performance from educational data. We believe that analyzing and studying the extracted dataset is important in order to understand the hidden information and help the tutors to enhance the overall performance for their students. This motivate us to apply a wrapper feature selection algorithm based on binary Genetic Algorithm (BGA) to reduce the data complexity and enhance the performance of machine learning classifiers.

III. PROPOSED HYBRID APPROACH

In this paper, a hybrid approach between BGA and several machine learning classifiers (i.e., 1D-CNN, kNN, SVM, NB and ANN) is proposed. The BGA works as a wrapper feature selection. Figure 1 presents the proposed hybrid approach. The following subsections presents the main components of the proposed hybrid approach.

A. Preprocessing

Preprocessing is an important step for any machine learning method. Here, we first make sure that the collected dataset has no missing data (i.e., records). We removed all missing data. Then, we normalized the dataset between [0,1] to make sure that the data type is consistent for all features (i.e., input).

B. Binary genetic algorithm

Genetic algorithm (GA) is one of the most successful evolutionary algorithm [22], that has been applied successfully in many domains [23], [24], [25]. In Simple, GA simulates the behavior of natural selection. GA is an iterative algorithm that starts by generate a set of solution called population. GA has three main functions (i.e., operators) which are selection, crossover, and mutation. The three operators are repeated until stop condition is reached (i.e., maximum number of iterations or optimal value) [22]. Figure 2 presents the pseudo-code for standard GA.

The performance of GA depends on GA operators, problem search space and size of population [26]. GA operators play an important role on the exploration and exploitation processes of GA. The first operator is selection. The selection process (e.g. select two solutions) using a well-known selection method (i.e. random, roulette wheel, or tournament) from the population. Then a crossover operation (i.e., single, double, uniform) will be performed. The last process is mutation, where the solution is updated using an elitism replacement strategy [27].

In this work, we convert the original GA (continuous) to a binary GA (discrete). To achieve this conversion, each solution is presented as a binary vector. Figure ?? presents the process of BGA for a single iteration. We used ANN as an internal classifier to evaluate the selected features, where the fitness function is presented in Eq.(1). Where E refers to the overall error rate, β refers to a fixed threshold value ($\beta = 5$), $|R|$ refers to the number of selected features, and $|N|$

Figure 1: Proposed methodology.

Given:

- nP: base population size.
- nI: number of iterations.
- rC: rate of crossover.
- rM: rate of mutation.

Generate initial population of size nP.
Evaluate initial population according to the fitness function.

While (*current_iteration* ≤ *nI*)

- //Breed $rC \times nP$ new solutions.
- Select two parent solutions from current population.
- Form offspring's solutions via crossover.
- IF** ($rand(0.0, 1.0) < rM$)
- Mutate the offspring's solutions.
- end IF**
- Evaluate each child solution according to the fitness function.
- Add offspring's to population.
- //population size is now $MaxPop = nP \times (1 + rC)$.
- Remove the $rC \times nP$ least-fit solutions from population.

end While
Output the global best solution

Figure 2: The pseudo-code for Genetic Algorithm.

IV. DATASET

A public educational dataset is used in this paper that is proposed by Cortez and Silva [28], [29] in 2008. The dataset presents secondary schools in Portugal. The secondary in Portugal consists of 3 years. While schools can be private and public one. The grading system range is between 0 and 20. For each semester, the students have to be evaluated three times. The dataset is collected from two public school during 2005-2006 academic year.

The final grade presents the target (i.e., student performance), that should be predicted. The dataset has 33 features (i.e., demographics, personal information, students marks, school information, etc.). The dataset presents the performance of the students in two subjects: (i) Mathematics (mat), and (ii) Portuguese language (por). Table II presents the 32 features and feature 33 presents the final target called G3. For more information and details about the dataset and how it is collected, readers can read [28]. The link of the dataset is <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/student+performance>.

V. PERFORMANCE MEASURE

To examine the performance of the proposed approach, we used four criteria which are: true positive (TP), true negative (TN), false positive (FP) and false negative (FN). Also, we used the confusion matrix (CM) as presented in Figure 4. CM is employed to find true positive rate (TPR), true negative rate (TNR), false positive rate (FPR) and false negative rate (FNR). From the previous metrics we calculate two main factors which are: accuracy (Eq.(2)), and Precision (Eq.(3)).

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + FN + TN} \quad (2)$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (3)$$

VI. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In this work, we simulates the proposed method to predict the students' performance. All experiments were executed on an Intel Core i7- 7700HQ 2.8-GHz computer with 16 GB RAM and all experiments were programmed using Matlab 2019b environment. In this paper, we performed two types of experiments: standard classifiers without BGA, and with BGA. We employed ANN as an internal classifier for BGA.

presents the total number of features. The parameters setting for internal classifier (ANN) is shown in Table I.

$$Fitness = E * (1 + \beta * \frac{|R|}{|N|}) \quad (1)$$

Table I: Parameters setting for ANN internal classifier.

Parameters	Values
Size of input layer	$ R $ number of selected features
Size of hidden layer	$ R /2$
Size of output layer	1
Training sample	75% of the data
Testing sample	15% of the data
Validation sample	10% of the data
Fitness function	Mean square error (MSE)

C. Classification methods

In this paper, we trained five different machine leaning models: NB, SVM, kNN, 1D-CNN, and ANN. All selected classifiers have been employed successfully in different domains. We trained all selected classifier for up to 300 epochs.

Figure 3: A demonstration of BGA for a single iteration [23].

		Predicted values		Totals
		Positive	Negative	
Actual Values	Positive	TP	FN	$P = (TP + FN) = \text{Actual Total Positives}$
	Negative	FP	TN	$N = (FP + TN) = \text{Actual Total Negatives}$
Totals		Predicted Total Positives	Predicted Total Negatives	

Figure 4: Confusion matrix.

In this work, we applied crossover validation with $kfold=10$. Table III explores the parameters setting for BGA used in this paper.

The first phase of our experiments is to execute the feature selection algorithm (i.e., BGA) on order to determine the most important feature and remove the irreverent/ redundant features. We executed BGA for 11 independent runs. Table IV explores the selected features for each run, fitness value and execution time. The selected features from run number 7 is considered the best features that help tutors and decision-makers to understand the factors that affects on the performance of their students.

Table V explores the average obtained results for all classifiers with and without feature selection. It is clear that BGA enhances the overall performance for all classifiers except NB

classifier. For example, the accuracy of SVM is improved 6% after applying BGA. Moreover, the performance of 1D-CNN with feature selection is outperforms other methods based on the average of accuracy (i.e., 90) and the average of Precision (i.e., 0.89). Figure 5 and Figure 6 explore the boxplot diagrams for all used classifiers with and without feature selection, respectively. Both Figures demonstrate Best, Worst, Average, and Median values. It is clear that the performance of 1D-CNN is more stable compared to other methods after removing the redundant features. While the performance of kNN is not stable.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we investigate the importance of applying a wrapper feature selection algorithm (i.e., BGA) to enhance the overall performance of machine learning classifiers. We

Table II: Dataset distribution.

Attribute	Description (Domain)
Sex	student's sex (binary: female or male)
Age	student's age (numeric: from 15 to 22)
school	student's school (binary: Gabriel Pereira or Mousinho da Silveira)
Address	student's home address type (binary: urban or rural)
Pstatus	parent's cohabitation status (binary: living together or apart)
Medu	mother's education (numeric: from 0 to 4 ^a)
Mjob	mother's job (nominal ^b)
Fedu	father's education (numeric: from 0 to 4 ^a)
Fjob	father's job (nominal ^b)
guardian	student's guardian (nominal: mother, father or other)
famsize	family size (binary: ≤ 3 or > 3)
famrel	quality of family relationships (numeric: from 1 – very bad to 5 – excellent)
reason	reason to choose this school (nominal: close to home, school reputation, course preference or other)
travelttime	home to school travel time (numeric: 1 – < 15 min., 2 – 15 to 30 min., 3 – 30 min. to 1 hour or 4 – > 1 hour).
studytime	weekly study time (numeric: 1-< 2 hours, 2-2 to 5 hours, 3-5 to 10 hours or 4-> 10 hours)
failures	number of past class failures (numeric: n if 1 ≤ n < 3, else 4)
schoolsup	extra educational school support (binary: yes or no)
famsup	family educational support (binary: yes or no)
activities	extra-curricular activities (binary: yes or no)
paidclass	extra paid classes (binary: yes or no)
internet	Internet access at home (binary: yes or no)
nursery	attended nursery school (binary: yes or no)
higher	wants to take higher education (binary: yes or no)
romantic	with a romantic relationship (binary: yes or no)
freetime	free time after school (numeric: from 1 – very low to 5 – very high)
goout	going out with friends (numeric: from 1 – very low to 5 – very high)
Walc	weekend alcohol consumption (numeric: from 1 – very low to 5 – very high)
Dalc	workday alcohol consumption (numeric: from 1 – very low to 5 – very high)
health	current health status (numeric: from 1 – very bad to 5 – very good)
absences	number of school absences (numeric: from 0 to 93)
G1	first period grade (numeric: from 0 to 20)
G2	second period grade (numeric: from 0 to 20)
G3	final grade (numeric: from 0 to 20)
a: 0 – none, 1 – primary education (4th grade), 2 – 5th to 9th grade, 3 – secondary education or 4 – higher education	
b: teacher, health care related, civil services (e.g. administrative or police), at home or other.	

Table III: The parameters setting for BGA.

Parameters	Values
Number of generation	500
Population size	150
Crossover rate	0.80
Mutation rate	0.02
Selection type	Roulette Wheel Selection (RWS)
Crossover type	Uniform

examine the proposed hybrid approach to predict students' performance. Here, we applied five different machine learning classifiers, which are: SVM, NB, kNN, 1D-CNN, and ANN. The obtained results show the most important features that each tutor should take care of it in order to enhance his/her students' performance. The performance of 1D-CNN outper-

forms other classifiers. In addition to that, we found that BGA is an outstanding approach that can help tutors and decision-makers to understand their educational data. In our future work, we plan to study different types or wrapper feature selection algorithms over different educational data.

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Table IV: Selected features from 11 independent runs by BGA.

	Selected Features										Fitness value	Execution time (sec.)
Run1	Fjob	famsize	failures	traveltime	internet	schoolsup	higher	G1	G2		0.0251	58.36
Run2	Sex	school	Mjob	famerl	traveltime	higher	G1	G2			0.0175	63.81
Run3	Pstatus	school	Sex	Age	reason	higher	G1	G2			0.0728	47.28
Run4	internet	activities	Medu	Fjob	Mjob	famsize	higher	health	G1	G2	0.0853	55.63
Run5	romantic	Sex	Age	school	famerl	G1	G2				0.0852	57.88
Run6	studytime	famsize	Sex	Address	activities	Pstatus	G1	G2			0.0756	69.36
Run7	school	health	Pstatus	famerl	Mjob	G1	G2				0.0158	68.57
Run8	Fjob	Mjob	Fedu	Sex	Age	higher	G1	G2			0.0188	77.63
Run9	internet	school	Medu	famerl	Age	reason	higher	G1	G2		0.0756	44.37
Run10	goout	romantic	Sex	Age	G1	G2					0.0823	53.89
Run11	activities	Fjob	Sex	famsize	higher	health	G1	G2			0.0875	51.28

Table V: The obtained results with and without BGA for all classifiers.

	With FS		Without FS	
	Accuracy	Precision	Accuracy	Precision
SVM	0.85	0.82	0.79	0.8
NB	0.81	0.87	0.77	0.85
kNN	0.81	0.78	0.8	0.72
1D-CNN	0.90	0.89	0.85	0.90
ANN	0.86	0.85	0.83	0.86

Figure 5: Boxplot diagram for all classifiers with BGA.

Figure 6: Boxplot diagram for all classifiers without BGA.

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